

Bioleaching of critical metals from spent lithium cobalt oxide batteries using *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans*

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The rapid expansion of portable electronics has led to a surge in Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), including large volumes of spent lithium-ion batteries. Among them, lithium cobalt oxide (LCO) batteries are a significant source of critical metals, particularly cobalt and lithium [1]. Traditional recycling methods, such as hydrometallurgy, though effective, involve high chemical consumption and environmental impact. As a sustainable alternative, bio-hydrometallurgy, and particularly bioleaching employs microorganisms for metal extraction, offering operational advantages such as lower energy input and reduced chemical usage [2,3].

This study investigates the bioleaching potential of the chemolithoautotrophic bacterium *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* for cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), lithium (Li) and copper (Cu) recovery from spent LCO batteries. Pre-treated spent LCO batteries material was subjected to a series of controlled bioleaching experiments under varying conditions, including pulp density, pH, temperature, and bacterial concentration. The bioleaching mechanism relies on the bacterium's ability to oxidize ferrous iron and sulphur compounds, generating ferric ions and sulfuric acid that facilitate metal solubilization from the LCO matrix.

Analytical techniques such as X-Ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF), atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), and scanning electron microscopy coupled with Energy Dispersive XRF (SEM-EDX) were used to monitor metal dissolution, structural changes in the leached material, and microbial interaction with the substrate. The determination of the bacterial growth was performed by measuring the optical density at 600 nm with a UV- VIS spectrophotometer. Sampling was performed by taking 2 mL samples at regular intervals to analyze the pH value, biomass concentration, organic acids and metal concentration. Results showed a maximum Co recovery of 64%, Ni 57%, Li 52% and Cu 81% under optimized conditions (L/S=100 ml/g, 20 ml of inoculum, T=30°C), with initial pH adjustment and over a period of 6 days.

These findings demonstrate the feasibility of *A. ferrooxidans*-assisted bioleaching as a viable green technology for the recovery of critical metals from spent LCO batteries. Ongoing work focuses on scaling the process and improving kinetics for industrial application.

References

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